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Brand's Image, Love, and Loyalty: Is it Enough for Word of Mouth Marketing?

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ABSTRACT

Laptop products are no longer luxury products, and they are commodities commonly used by university students. However yet, every laptop brand has its brand image in the market. Also, Brand love and loyalty have become central concepts in brand and customer relationships. This paper investigates the effects of 'brand image on brand love' and 'brand love on customer loyalty' and 'word-of-mouth (WOM) marketing'. Additionally, it investigates which phases of loyalty have priority in creating WOM. Questionnaires had distributed to 300 college students to collect data. Structural equation modeling (SEM) had used to analyze the hypothesis, and from Multi Criteria Decision Making methods, TOPSIS was used to rank the priority of the phases of loyalty. Analyses show that brand love and image remarkably effect on brand loyalty. In addition, it has been determined that brand love affects WOM. The TOPSIS results also reveal that affective loyalty has priority effective on WOM. Other predictors are cognitive, behavioral, and cognitive loyalty, respectively. The results can help practitioners engage customers while creating a brand image and marketing their laptop brands to construct loyal customer support. The ranking of the type of loyalty can also ensure a phase for marketers to develop future strategies.

Keywords: Brand Image, Brand Loyalty, Brand Love, Word of Mouth, Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), TOPSIS Method

Introduction

It is known that brands convey the aspects they want consumers to see with the image they have. However, in today's conditions, this is not enough to convince the consumer. Consumers caught in the information bombardment have the right to choose from almost countless alternatives. For this reason, brands need to get the best they can get with the image they offer to consumers. The notion of brand love is one of the essential that brands hope to win. If the

consumer is in love with the brand, it would be loyal to the brand. Moreover, if the consumer is in love with the brand, even it will do marketing for the brand.

On the other hand, technology is changing with innovation and progress to meet human needs and wants. Together with technology, it has seen the usage of laptops is increasing step by step. Furthermore, laptops can use anytime, anywhere for communication, transferring, and accessing information. Moreover, Laptop products are no longer luxury products, but they are commodities commonly used by university students. However yet, every laptop brand has its brand image in the market. Because of its high discernibility, the consumers are image and brand-aware, which is reflected in laptops' buying decisions. As long as the brand can maintain this image, it will be successful by creating love and loyalty. In this way, consumers' tendency to share positive information will increase, a brand that complies with needs and desires will be embraced by consumers.

In the first part of the study, a literature review has been done on the concepts of image, love, loyalty, and WOM. Then, in the second part, information about the purpose, method, model, and study hypotheses are given. Finally, readers can read some suggestions for marketers and the sector in the conclusion part.

Brand Image

The brand image is as the customers' current view of a brand (Emari et al., 2012). Researchers have maintained that brand image is a fundamental component of strong brands, which facilitates firms to differentiate their products/brands from other firms. Also, it has a unique power about the brand association in the customer's mind (Taylor et al., 2007). The brand name's awareness is a primary and noteworthy element of the process, and the name is the base of the brand's image (Zeynalzade, 2012). Because the better and more positive the image of a brand, consumers will remember it. To be accomplished in the market, companies must build a positive image from the company's beginning (Chakraborty & Bhat, 2018).

Boo et al. (2009) argued that brand image considered consumers' reasoned or emotional perception attached to particular brands. Therefore, a positive brand image reveals the desire for loving these brands among consumers. Likewise, Ismail and Spinelli (2012) observed a positive relation among brand image and brand love. Also, brand image has been an essential source of brand love (Sallam, 2014).

H1: Brand image has a positive impact on brand love.

Brand Love

Of late years it is seen that tremendous research interest in love. Specifically, marketing analysts examined the brand love concept (Ahuvia, 2005). Some of them defined love for a brand as "*the degree of passionate, emotional attachment that a person has for a particular trade name.*" (Carroll & Ahuvia, 2006). For instance, Albert et al. (2008) assert that consumers' love involve specific following the characteristics: "*passion for a brand, brand attachment, positive evaluation of the brand, positive emotions in response to the brand, and declarations of love toward the brand.*" At the same time, companies recognize that the feeling of love toward a brand is a necessary determinant in assigning a great connection with a customer. Thus, those companies that can make customers love their brands gain a sustainable competitive advantage (Roberts, 2006).

It also represents the feelings of sincerity and passion towards a brand, respectively, of like and desire. Similarly, at the cognitive level, decision refers to recognizing the individual's liking and desire for the brand in the short term. Brand loyalty means buying the same brand over and over again, today and in the future. In this sense, brand love is significant in marketing as it is positively associated with brand loyalty and word of mouth (Bergkvist & Bech-Larsen, 2010). The basic idea behind WOM; is sharing positive or negative emotions, opinions, and information by consumers that guide direct buyers (Mothersbaugh et al., 2019). If the consumers like the product/brand, they will share it with others. The system is that simple and clear.

H2: Brand love has a positive impact on brand loyalty.

H3: Brand love has a positive impact on WOM.

Brand Loyalty

Aaker (1991) explains brand loyalty as a condition that indicates how likely a customer is to switch to a different brand, especially if that brand changes in price or product features. Otherwise, Chaudhuri (1995) expresses that brand loyalty is a consumer's option to purchase a specific brand in a product category. At the same time, this situation arises due to the perceived quality of the brand, not the price. Although some points differ in the definitions, there is a joint inference. Brand loyalty is the consumer's intention to repurchase a product in the future and/or a commitment to remain loyal to the brand to become a regular customer (Kim et al., 2008; Emari et al., 2012).

Oliver (1999) has expressed the four-stage loyalty model. These Loyalty Phases are; *cognitive, affective, conative, and behavioral*. If explained briefly, according to cognitive loyalty, consumers make choices based on their knowledge of the brand or their experiences. It is based on information such as price, features (Back & Parks, 2003). Affective loyalty emerges from consumers' liking and satisfaction with the brand (Oliver, 1997). Conative loyalty is a behavioral result. If there is conative loyalty, the consumer tends an intention to re-buy the brand. Finally, in behavioral loyalty, the purchasing intention and desire of the consumer turn into purchasing behavior. This current study examined brand loyalty in four dimensions: *cognitive, affective, conative, and behavioral*.

Other hands, loyal customers generate positive word-of-mouth (Jain et al., 2018). Casaló et al. (2008) also suggest that loyal customers will provide honest recommendations and word of mouth to other customers. Kazemi et al. (2013) studied the impact of brand loyalty on WOM, and they found that brand loyalty has a positive relationship with WOM (Niyomsart & Khamwon, 2015).

H4: Brand loyalty has a positive impact on WOM.

Word of Mouth

The concept of word of mouth refers to the main informal mode of communication of consumers. In the early definitions, word of mouth was defined as the face-to-face communication of at least two consumers about brands/products or services without a commercial purpose (Godes & Mayzlin, 2004). Then, with communication channels, WOM communication attained interest among the societal relations. As a result, it has become one of the most important and powerful communication channels. WOM describes as "*informal*,

person to person communication between a perceived non-commercial communicator and a receiver regarding a brand, a product, an organization or a service." (Harrison-Walker, 2001). WOM's power comes from a non-commercial process because information about brand/products/services, shops, firms, and all can spread out from consumer to consumer others without non-commercial intent.

When consumers feel that they love and/or are committed to the brand, they are likely to recommend the brand to their friends and other people. Therefore, many people use WOM to inform other people. This information can be positive or negative. Moreover, much previous research found a strong connection between brand love, loyalty, and customers' WOM (Albert et al., 2008; Ismail & Spinelli, 2012; Sallam, 2014; Kiuru, 2016; Ayuningsih & Maftukhah, 2020).

Research Methodology

Research design

The study investigates the effects of brand image on brand love and brand love on customer loyalty and word-of-mouth (WOM) marketing. Additionally, it investigates which phases of loyalty have priority in creating WOM. Thus, suggestions will be made to brands in a tough competition battle in the electronic/technological product market, such as laptop brands. WOM is the most potent weapon of marketers. If this power comes from brand loyalty, brands will obtain a significant competitive advantage.

The questionnaire includes all the constructs in the research model to explore the hypotheses. The questionnaire takes the place of two parts. The first part of the survey was designed to measure the study's variables by considering a laptop brand that the participants used. The questionnaire is prepared in 5 points Likert Scale. In the study, revised brand image scale from Salinas and Perez (2009); brand love scale from Carroll and Ahuvia (2006); brand loyalty from Chaudhuri and Holbrook (2001) and Kumari and Patyal (2017); word of mouth from Babin et al. (2005) and Yu and Dean (2001).

Three hundred college-level students from Samsun province who use laptops were selected through the convenience sampling method to gather the data to meet the research objectives. The scope of the research consists of college students. This group attracts the attention of many units, especially in recent years, due to their increasing buying capacity, technology usage habits, and their tendency to spend money on technological tools. In addition, young consumers prefer products that strengthen their self-image due to their sensitivity to themselves. Furthermore, they are conscious of brand image, status and they use word of mouth communication effectively. Therefore, Laptop brands are considered as the content of this study as it is common among young people.

Moreover, when consumers are pleased with the laptop brand, they have trends to brand love, brand loyalty, and positive WOM. Before participating in the questionnaire, asked to all participants control question and only participants using laptops were included in the study.

In the study, testing the recommended study focus and hypotheses were managed through three steps: *i)* assessment of reliability analysis, factor analysis, and demographic status of the sample with SPSS, *ii)* assessment of the structural model with SEM, and *iii)* assessment of the ranking of the priority of brand loyalty phases with TOPSIS.

Figure 1. The relation among the variables

Results of Analysis

i) Assessment of Reliability Analysis, Factor Analysis, and Demographic Status

The sample was 167 male respondents (55,7%) and 133 female respondents (44,3%). Respondents whose ages from 18 to 25 made up 83,3%; from 26 to 30, made up 16,7%. Table 1 explained that the result of Cronbach's Alpha and Exploratory Factor analysis and AVE and CR results. The table also shows that Cronbach's alpha values of the independent variables were above 0,70. Therefore, constructs reached internal consistency reliability.

Table 1. Measurement Results of the Factor Construct's

Construct	Items	Factor Loading	Construct	Items	Factor Loading
<i>Brand Image</i>	BI1	,844	<i>Brand Loyalty</i>	BHRL1	,865
	BI2	,872		BHRL2	,934
	BI3	,545		BHRL3	,929
	BI4	,746		BHRL4	,886
	BI5	,852		BHRL5	,699
	BI6	,762		BHRL6	,736
	BI7	,857		BHRL7	,914
	BI8	,775		BHRL8	,881
<i>Brand Love</i>	BL1	,832	ATTL1	,736	$\alpha = 0,955$ CR= 0,797 AVE= 0,604
	BL2	,860	ATTL2	,629	
	BL3	,859	ATTL3	,593	
	BL4	,915	ATTL4	,875	
	BL5	,871	ATTL5	,894	
	BL6	,849	ATTL6	,909	
	BL7	,593	ATTL7	,912	
	BL8	,749	ATTL8	,925	
	BL9	,880	ATTL9	,896	
	BL10	,828			
Word of Mouth	WOM1	,884			$\alpha = 0,874$ CR=0,847 AVE=0,501
	WOM2	,900			
	WOM3	,898			

According to Awang and his colleague (2015), the average variance (AVE) should be more than 0,50 for validity. At the same time, composite reliability (CR) should be 0,70 or higher. Results show that composite reliability is provided for constructs.

ii) Assessment of The Structural Model

Figure 2 and Table 2 showed the results of the SEM. Chi-square=5,260 df=3 and $X^2/df=1,753$ was significant at 0,05 level ($p=0,00$). SRMR; is the square root of the standardized mean errors. Since the SRMR is less than 0.08, it can be said that the research model has a good model fit (Garson, 2016; Cuong, 2020). Results state that the model had SRMR indices=0,009<0,08. Furthermore, the model elicits a good fit with the data AGFI=0,965 GFI=0,993 TLI=0,989, CFI=0,997, and RMSEA=0.050 (Hair, 2018).

Figure 2. Structural model
(*the standardized path estimates and ** the t-values)

Viewing the study results suggests that brand image has the most significant contribution to the development of brand love. Similarly, brand loyalty has a strong effect on WOM. Moreover, brand love has a significant effect on both loyalty and WOM.

Table 2. Summary of Hypothesis-testing Results.

Paths	Hypotheses	Path coefficients	(t) Value	p value	Result
Brand Image → Brand Love	H1	0,94	11,24	0,000	Accepted
Brand Love → Brand Loyalty	H2	0,54	5,72	0,000	Accepted
Brand Love → WOM	H3	0,39	3,03	0,000	Accepted
Brand Loyalty → WOM	H4	0,72	7,83	0,000	Accepted

iii) Assessment of The Ranking of The Priority of Brand Loyalty Phases

TOPSIS (Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution) is one method of multi-criteria decision-making. Multi-criteria decision making is the desire of human beings to make the calculated decision in a situation of multiple selections. TOPSIS is the method to improve analytical and numerical methods that consider multiple alternatives with multiple criteria. This method is an extensively applicable method with an elementary mathematical model (Pavić & Novoselac, 2013). Moreover, as TOPSIS applied with Excel in this study, it is a very suitable practical method based on computer support.

TOPSIS method had used to find out in what order of importance brand loyalty affects WOM. Furthermore, this method aimed to express which order of brand loyalty phases affects motivate individuals to WOM.

In the TOPSIS method, in which the options (alternatives) are sorted according to specific parameters (criteria), the following procedures have been applied; in the first step, the decision matrix had created. Later, based on the decision matrix, the normalized decision matrix was obtained. Then, the distances to the ideal solution and the negative ideal solution had calculated. Finally, the alternatives' ranking was made by calculating each alternative's relative scores (Pavić & Novoselac, 2013). Due to the lengthy theoretical explanation of the method, only the final step had expressed in the notation below. However, this method is applied in the last three decades (Hwang et al., 1993; Wei, 2010; Dutta et al., 2021), and there are many papers on its applications (Yoon & Hwang, 1995; Marler & Arora, 2010; Tzeng & Huang, 2011; Xu & Tao, 2019).

In the last stage of TOPSIS, the relative affinity (C_i^x) values of the ideal solution had used in ordering the alternatives. To calculate this value, ideal distance (S_i^x) and negative ideal distance (S_i^-) values are needed. These values had obtained with the help of the formula below.

$$S_i^* = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (v_{ij} - v_j^*)^2} \quad S_i^- = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (v_{ij} - v_j^-)^2}$$

After the calculation of the distance values, the C_i^x Value had calculated with the following formula, and the relevant values had obtained which are shown in Table 3.

$$C_i^* = \frac{S_i^-}{S_i^- + S_i^*}$$

Table 3. Results and Evaluation of Ranking

Alternatives	S_i^x	S_i^-	C_i^x	Ranking
<i>Behavioral loyalty</i>	0,014	0,162	0,918	3
<i>Cognitive loyalty</i>	0,014	0,165	0,922	2
<i>Affective loyalty</i>	0,000	0,225	1,000	1
<i>Conative loyalty</i>	0,030	0,000	0,000	4

According to the results, the most effective loyalty phase that motivates individuals to WOM is affective loyalty. Affective loyalty emerges as a result of consumers' liking and satisfaction with the brand. Also, considering that WOM is a process that emerges with the emotions of individuals after their purchase, this result is consistent. Individuals who do not feel emotionally close or dislike will not recommend brands to their friends and relatives. So, one more time, emotions have been very decisive in decisions.

On the other hand, it had seen that the results are close to each other. Cognitive and behavioral loyalty have very close results. This situation had thought to be related to the product category examined in the study. Although laptop brands create affective loyalty, they go through cognitive and behavioral processes in the minds of consumers as technological products. Consumers create WOM depending on the knowledge they have about their laptop brands or experience with the brand. Then, they recommend to others that they can buy these brands. Conative loyalty is in the last rank. Conative loyalty is related to an individual's intention to

buy again. Hence, it is at the end of the rank to effecting WOM because re-purchase decisions are not the most curious or priority issues of WOM content.

Discussion

This study aimed to survey the relationship and effect of brand image, brand love, and brand loyalty on WOM. Also, it investigates which phases of loyalty have priority in creating WOM. Results of SEM analysis state that brand image plays a importance role and strongly impacts the brand love for laptops in college-level students ($\beta=0,94$). Similarly, brand loyalty plays an important role and positively affects the WOM about laptops ($\beta=0,72$) in college students because they perceive that the brand image increases brand love and loyalty. The sooner practical studies support the consequence of this study (Casaló et al., 2008; Ismail & Spinelli, 2012; Sallam, 2014; Jain et al., 2018). Besides, the outcomes state out that brand love had a critical positive effect on brand loyalty ($\beta=0,54$) and WOM. Nonetheless, the effect size of the connection of brand love and brand loyalty was partly small from others ($\beta=0,39$). Therefore, the earlier empirical studies confirmed the consequence of this study (Mothersbaugh et al., 2019; Bergkvist & Bech-Larsen, 2010).

TOPSIS results show that the 'affective loyalty' phase has the most effect on word of mouth. When customers have loyalty towards a brand/company, their tendency to share their positive feelings with other people increases. Previous research confirms this result. It shows that loyal customers are more likely to engage in positive word-of-mouth than others (Srinivasan et al. 2002; Yeh & Choi, 2011; Hsu et al. 2013; Markovic et al., 2018). It is seen that a similar positive relationship exists between affective loyalty and positive word of mouth (Harrison-Walker, 2001; Royo Vela & Casamassima, 2011; Choi & Choi, 2014). Therefore, customers whose emotional ties become even stronger after brand loyalty, indicates stronger customer affection, will likely engage in positive word-of-mouth (Choi and Choi, 2014). Yu and Dean (2001) state that the affective phase is a better predictor of customer loyalty than the cognitive phase. Further, the researchers point out the affective loyalty is the best predictor of positive word of mouth and the most reliable dimension of overall loyalties.

Roy and colleagues (2009) examined the influence of the loyalty phases on the word-of-mouth communication of online retail store customers. They had collected data from a similar sample with this study and estimated the path coefficients between the loyalty states and the WOM behavior via SEM. Their ranking is affective, conative, behavioral, and cognitive (in terms of β). While their work focuses on the service brand, this work is based on the laptop brand. Considering this situation, the displacement of cognitive and cognitive loyalty is consistent. This information also shows that the TOPSIS ranking result is consistent.

Theoretical and Practical Implications

In recent years, companies invest prominent resources to improve brands with a assertive image more than ever. Together with other brand advantages, a assertive image facilitates company expansion through brand extensions. In this way, products with the same brand name can benefit from the overall image, awareness and brand equity of the brand (Salinas & Perez, 2009).

On the other part, the laptop companies have to consider customers' expectations and identify the factors that highly influence the consumers' WOM behavior about their laptops. Thus, they

could prepare convenient marketing plans and brand strategies to attain organizational goals and objectives. The findings obtained in this study will help better to understand brand preference practices of the laptop market. Results also help us know how WOM is involved in image, love, loyalty, and brand searching, analyzing its attributes and brand choice. In this way, it will also be helpful to build up the profile of a specific consumer for a specific brand. In addition, the marketers can also trace out the important reasons for love, loyalty, and WOM.

The paper provides some expressive throw-around for practitioners as well. Youth forms a large technology market segment in most country as Turkey. It display a desire for universal brands as a statement of brand loyalty. Therefore, the findings purpose that marketers should make an effort to brand their laptops and involve consumers in the process. In this way, customer loyalty will be increased. When the brand image is attractive and improves one's self-image and self-identity, consumers will likely trend to brand (Hansen & Jensen, 2009). Therefore marketers can reinforce their brand image. Also, a strong brand provides more customer love and loyalty to the firm. More importantly, it provides benefits such as the customer showing flexibility to price changes (Kim et al., 2015).

Considering the impressive influence of affective loyalty on WOM behavior, laptop companies need to offer emotional content to their customers on various platforms such as social media and brand pages. It can also track customer conversations to know better the brands customers love and the images they consider ideal. Text mining is a modern method for this case. In this way, marketers will help young customers create brands that raise their self-image. In addition, marketers must ensure that customers relate their lifestyles to laptop brands while communicating their brand messages. For this reason, it is necessary to take into account the impressions in social media promotion and advertising works. In particular, attention should be paid to how it is said, more than what is said. The previous study indicates that Gen X buyers make their buying analytically based upon value because these generation trust the brand's symbolic features, images, and feelings rather than the functional features related to the purchase (Heine, 2010; Park & Yang, 2010; Islam & Rahman, 2016). These situations exhibit that young people are prone to emotional decision-making and also support the analysis result.

Limitations and Suggestions for Future Study

This study is thought to contribute to the marketing scientific area. But of course, it has some limitations. The first is that the size of sample and it is relatively small. The respondents of this study are only Ondokuz Mayıs University students. Future research can consider a more extensive and different sample size handling alternative sampling methods to provide generalizability. Also, current research just measures the effects of brand image, love, loyalty, and WOM. Future researchers should focus on different impacts variables for instance brand equity, brand attitude, brand satisfaction, brand trust, brand preference.

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Conflict of Interests

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